

ISSUES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND CRAFT DEVELOPMENT IN THE NEIGHBORHOODS

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Abstract. *This article covers the issues of development of entrepreneurship and crafts in neighborhoods.*

Key words: *mahalla, entrepreneurship, business, crafts in mahallas, population, income.*

In the concept of the formation of civil society and deepening of democratic reforms in the country, the issue of turning the neighborhood into a center for the development of private entrepreneurship and family business is defined. Laws "On Family Business" and "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" were adopted in a new version, legal guarantees in this area were strengthened. Today, the neighborhood is playing an important role in encouraging the development of small businesses. Self-government bodies of citizens support entrepreneurs in every way, new productions opening helps restore national crafts. At the same time, the economic activity of the population, the social responsibility of business for creative work in neighborhoods is increasing.

At the present time, the development of crafts and entrepreneurship in neighborhoods is considered as the main direction of providing employment to the population of our country and ending poverty. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 3, 2021 "On measures to organize the activities of mayor's assistants on the issues of developing entrepreneurship in the neighborhood, ensuring population employment and reducing poverty" defined specific tasks for the mayor's assistants. For 2022, the sources of financial instruments used by assistant mayors in the performance of their duties are as follows: a) loans allocated within the framework of family business development programs - 10 trillion soums; b) funds allocated for ensuring the employment of the population, their self-employment, as well as the establishment of entrepreneurial activities - 1,218 billion soums, of which: 785 billion soums for subsidies, credit resources and other expenses for the unemployed population for entrepreneurship and self-employment from the state employment assistance fund, 210 billion soums for directing the unemployed population to study for professions, entrepreneurship and crafts; 222 billion soums were allocated from the Public Works Fund for the cost of involving the unemployed

population in paid public works. Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev announced new measures to support textiles, furniture, jewelry and a number of other industries. The task of localizing at least 50 types of new products was assigned to the association "Uztoqiliksanoat". Commercial banks allocated 100 million dollars for the development of such projects, and 50 million dollars for carpet production. The state covers 70% of the transportation costs for the export of fabric and knitwear to Europe, Turkey, Egypt, and Morocco. In general, the President emphasized the need to develop the textile industry with a new dynamic, programs for the export of industrial products in the next year, which will allocate more than 5 billion dollars, were adopted.

According to Decree No. PF-29 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 3, 2021 "On the priority directions of the state policy on the development of entrepreneurship in the neighborhood, ensuring population employment and reducing poverty", financial support for the implementation of entrepreneurial initiatives of the population, further improvement of the mechanisms of ensuring their employment with profitable work, reduction of poverty by bringing the neighborhood work system to a new level, shown in the republic, region, district and cities in order to bring state services and targeted financial support instruments directly to the neighborhood level, starting from January 1, 2022, in each town, village, village, as well as in each neighborhood (hereinafter - neighborhoods) in cities, towns, villages, and villages (hereinafter - neighborhoods) the position of the district (city) hokim's assistant (hereinafter referred to as the assistant hokim) was established for issues of provision and poverty reduction.

Our country is famous for its long tradition of furniture production. About 100 neighborhoods in Bukhara, Namangan, Samarkand, Andijan, Fergana and Khorezm specialize in this profession. The President emphasized the need to establish furniture industry centers around these neighborhoods in order to expand the conditions for craftsmen. The task of extending the period of validity of customs privileges for furniture manufacturers until January 1, 2024, and increasing the number of projects in this field was assigned. There are also wide possibilities in jewelry. Our country has a jewelry market worth 300 million dollars. This demand can easily be met by local jewelers. Therefore, a number of benefits aimed at supporting them have been established. In particular, a guarantee from any bank and export promotion agency is acceptable for deferred payment for gold and silver. This option has also been introduced for individual jewelers. The license requirement for temporary import and export of raw materials for jewelry has been abolished, and precious and decorative stones have been exempted from customs duties. The neighborhood policy aims to

solve three important tasks. The first is a spiritual task, which consists in restoring and developing the unique, dearest traditions and values of the thousand-year history of the Uzbek people. The second is a political task, which consists in restoring the neighborhood institution in accordance with the requirements of today's times and expanding its authority to manage society. The third and most important thing is that the neighborhood is not only a residential area, but also a center for the development of handicrafts and entrepreneurship, which should make a significant contribution to increasing the potential of our country to create material goods and various services.

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